

Design of a Control System for an Assistive Hand Exoskeleton

Irene Cardello
CREO Lab
Univ. Campus Bio-Medico
di Roma
Rome, Italy
irene.cardello@unicampus.it

Alessandro Ceccarelli
CREO Lab
Univ. Campus Bio-Medico
di Roma
Rome, Italy
a.ceccarelli@unicampus.it

Loredana Zollo
CREO Lab
Univ. Campus Bio-Medico
di Roma
Rome, Italy
l.zollo@unicampus.it

Fabrizio Taffoni
CREO Lab
Univ. Campus Bio-Medico
di Roma
Rome, Italy
f.taffoni@unicampus.it

Abstract—The loss of hand function can significantly impact an individual ability to perform activities of daily living, leading to decreased independence, potentially resulting in a decline in overall well-being. In this context, robotic aids, particularly exoskeletons or robotic wearable devices, have shown the potential to significantly enhance the autonomy of individuals in their everyday activities. This work, as part of the 3D-AID project, is focused on the development of a control unit for a portable and wearable low-cost hand assistive exoskeleton.

Keywords—Hand exoskeleton, embedded control, assistive device

I. INTRODUCTION

Hand functions can be impaired by various pathologies, including trauma, vascular conditions, cancer, and neurological disorders [1]. Robots serve as powerful tools for restoring hand functionality, either through rehabilitation programs or by providing direct assistance during Activities of daily living (ADLs) [2].

Figure 1: Block diagram of the 3D-AID hand exoskeleton with details on the mechanical interface for finger assistance: (a) prototype; (b) kinematic diagram of the mechanism for long fingers. Grey links represent the human phalanges, while yellow rotary joints represent the MCP, PIP, and DIP human joints.

When reviewing the literature on hand exoskeletons [2], one can observe a wide range of technologies and approaches. Exoskeletons may be fully actuated or use under-actuation strategies, i.e., when the Degrees of Freedom (DoFs) exceed the Degrees of Actuation (DoAs). They may be equipped with various actuation systems (electrical, pneumatic, hydraulic, thermal), employ different transmission strategies (depending on the intended use and the target condition to be assisted), and use diverse methods for motion intention acquisition. The 3D-AID project aims to develop low-cost hand exoskeletons for assisting with low-effort ADLs. The 3D-AID exoskeleton consists of three submodules (Figure 1.): i) an interface for physiological signal acquisition, ii) a mechanical interface for finger assistance, and iii) the control unit for motion intention detection and low-level electronic interface and control.

This work aims to present the preliminary development of the control unit for motion intention detection and device control. The proposed module consists of a dedicated electronic board and a firmware library to control up to 2 DoAs commanded by physiological signals (i.e. implicit control, [2]). To ensure the necessary adaptability during ADLs, the motion intention acquisition is based on an EMG interface [3], while the low-level control of the device is carried out monitoring system position and the torque overall provided.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The hand exoskeleton developed in the 3D-AID project within the collaboration between UCBM and Centro Protesi INAIL, integrates a previously designed mechanical interface for finger assistance, based on a rigid linkage system. It consists of 1-DoF kinematic chains scalable according to patients' size as presented in [4] for a finger prosthesis, and of a dorsal hand support. In this first release, the device assists the thumb and the index fingers allowing the execution of pinch/precision and of lateral grasping, which are involved in several ADLs. The system is fully actuated by DC motors to facilitate the use of the device in unstructured environments. Based on the mechanical structure, Actuonix L12 linear DC actuators ($V_s = 6V$; $I_{max} = 460mA$) with built-in position sensors were selected. The actuator rod has been directly coupled to the kinematic chain at the proximal link allowing a complete finger flexion with a stroke up to 10 mm.

The interface for EMG acquisition consists of two Ottobock MyoBock 13E200 superficial electrodes, positioned on the patient's forearm to detect the activation of flexor and extensor muscles [5]. Sensors have a bandwidth between [90-450] Hz according to their manual. The acquisition of these signals aims at detecting the direction of movement the user desires to perform (i.e. finger flexion or extension) and the velocity of execution (which it was supposed proportional to the EMG signal intensity).

The control unit should be equipped with a motor driver, enabling to control the velocity and the direction of movement of each actuator. To enable the simultaneous operation of the two Actuonix linear motors, the driver should allow delivering up to 1 A at 6 V. To monitor the hand position and the interaction forces exchanged with objects, the control unit should also allow to acquire the position of the rod, and the torque provided by actuators, while motion intention is derived from the acquisition of the EMG analogic signals. Overall, the control unit has to manage 6 analogic inputs (i.e. 2 EMGs; 2 Positions; 2 Torques) and 6 digital

outputs (i.e. 4 signals to set direction, and 2 PWMs to set velocity). The sampling frequency of analogic signal should be at least 1 kHz to avoid aliasing in EMG, and the ADC resolution up to 10 bits (a higher resolution is used for clinical EMG systems, and it is not necessary for the specific application). The control unit should be worn by the subject in a comfortable way to facilitate the use of the device. We selected the forearm as the target site with the long-term goal of developing a smart armband that also embeds EMG sensors. In this first release, the control unit has been embedded in a case integrating the power supply source but not the EMG sensors. Overall, the case should be compatible with the adult forearm dimension (i.e. 250 mm, radiale-stylylion length; 285 mm, forearm circumference, flexed [7]).

III. RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

Figure 2 shows a functional block diagram of the control unit with the main hardware components selected to meet the requirements detailed above.

Figure 2: Block diagram of the control unit

The control unit integrates a microcontroller PIC16F886 provided with 35 I/O pins, (14 analog inputs), a 10-bit ADC, 2 PWM output pins, 3 programmable. The motor driver has been developed using the L298 chip ($V_{max}=46V$; $I_{max,DC}=2A$): it integrates two H-bridges for controlling velocity and direction of the linear actuators. Each bridge has been equipped with R_{sENS} series resistor to the ground, allowing the estimation of the motor torque from the voltage drops ($V_{sENS,1/2}$). Voltage drops are amplified ($K_{sENS}=48$) to exploit full ADC range (Figure 3.a). A preliminary test has been carried out using breakout components to simulate different load conditions. The hardware has been powered with a digital bench power supply. Overall, the hardware drained a maximum of 1.0 A at 7.2 V. For this reason, two Li-Ion batteries (FBK 1865026, 3.6 V, 2600 mAh) connected in series, have been selected. This model guarantees 3 hours of autonomy in continuous operation. Due to the choice to use a series of two Li-Ion batteries a power management module has been integrated into the control unit. The module consists of a protection circuit against polarity reversal and overcurrent conditions as well as a block of voltage regulation to provide the lower constant voltage level required by the logical components. Finally, a PCB integrating the components detailed above has been designed

together with the case to house both the board and the batteries. The case has a volume of $47 \times 100 \times 45 \text{ mm}^3$ and its overall weight, together with the control unit and the batteries, is estimated to be 160 g.

Figure 3: (a) details on motor driver circuitry (a single H-Bridge is represented); (b) control logic implemented.

Figure 3.b shows the logic implemented in the first release of control firmware. A threshold on the EMG signals has been defined to detect motion intention. Motors are switched off in resting condition or in case of co-contraction. Additionally, they are switched off when torque or position reach limits internally set for safety purpose. Laboratory tests on the integrated electronics are running on. before testing the system with patients.

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